

DEVELOPMENT OF AN HPC BENCHMARK

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ABSTRACT

Adoption of HPC resources presents unique challenges for data-driven workloads at scale. With the increased specialization of storage solutions and topologies available, HPC users must now match their application I/O profile to the correct backing storage solution to achieve optimal performance. This project involves the investigation and development on a novel application-characterized I/O benchmark that may allow HPC users to benchmark a given storage implementation against their specific application I/O requirements at scale. Results of tests on single-process applications show that it possible to approximate the I/O workloads precisely with a low-level instrumentation tool. On the other hand, bandwidths (write and read rates) are much more challenging to approximate, in particular due to page caching. Further development is needed to extend this to applications that use a parallel protocol, such as MPI, and modern solutions such as containerized applications.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	3
2	METHODS	3
2.1	Toolkit	3
2.2	I/O profiling with Darshan	4
2.2.1	Limitations	4
2.3	IOR	5
2.4	Translating I/O requirements	6
2.4.1	Number of tasks (numTasks)	6
2.4.2	Transfer size	6
2.4.3	Block size	7
2.4.4	Number of segments (segmentCount)	7
3	TESTS AND RESULTS	7
3.1	Write tests	8
3.2	Read tests	9
4	RECOMMENDATIONS AND FUTURE WORK	10
5	REFERENCES	10

1 INTRODUCTION

Adoption of HPC resources presents unique challenges for data-driven workloads at scale. Big data applications depend on performant storage and connectivity to support the demanding IO requirements of modern workflows. With the increased specialization of storage solutions and topologies available, HPC users must now match their application I/O profile to the correct backing storage solution to achieve optimal performance. Therefore, this project proposes investigation and development on a novel application-characterized I/O benchmark for storage solutions that may allow HPC users to benchmark a given storage implementation against their specific application I/O requirements at scale.

All the code is available at: <https://gitlab.cern.ch/mguarand/openlab-hpc>, a Gitlab repository from CERN.

2 METHODS

The project is conceived as follows: we will handle as input any executable program (Python file, C executable, etc.). Darshan will be used to extract information about the I/O requirements of the program. This information is then processed and passed to IOR, which will finally benchmark and show the performance of the program in a given HPC environment. A sketch of the pipeline is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Pipeline of the project.

A lot of programs used at CERN are not parallelized at first, but are single-process programs. Therefore, and for the sake of simplicity, we will focus our efforts first on this type of applications. The results can then be extended to applications that use, for example, the MPI protocol or HDF5 datasets.

2.1 Toolkit

- **Darshan**: library for I/O characterization. We used version 3.3.1.
- **IOR**: benchmark for parallel file systems using various access patterns.
- **Slurm**: cluster management and job scheduling system.

The working environment was provided by the Flatiron Institute (FI). We worked on the Rusty cluster, where we experimented with the rome nodes, that share a 1.6 Tb/s link from the facility where they are located to the central storage resources at FI.

2.2 I/O profiling with Darshan

Darshan is an HPC I/O profiling characterization tool, meaning that it gives information about I/O operations called during a program execution. An application that has been instrumented with Darshan will produce a single log (binary) file each time it is executed. This log summarizes the I/O access patterns used by the application. To be able to read the information contained in this summary, one must use one of the 'Darshan utilities', whether it is to parse this log file into plain text or to get a higher-level PDF summary with graphics. For our purpose of handling precise information of I/O requirements and passing it to IOR, we will not care that much for the latter utility, except for debugging purposes. An example of the output of the darshan-parser utility, which outputs a plain text file, is shown in Figure 2.

#<module>	<rank>	<record id>	<counter>	<value>	<file name>	<mount pt>	<fs type>
649	0	15483593433758586291	POSIX_RENAME_TARGETS	0	/home/belen/github/cern/test_dir/output.9	/	ext4
650	0	15483593433758586291	POSIX_RENAME_TARGETS	0	/home/belen/github/cern/test_dir/output.9	/	ext4
651	0	15483593433758586291	POSIX_RENAME_FROM	0	/home/belen/github/cern/test_dir/output.9	/	ext4
652	0	15483593433758586291	POSIX_MODE	0	/home/belen/github/cern/test_dir/output.9	/	ext4
653	0	15483593433758586291	POSIX_BYTES_READ	14	/home/belen/github/cern/test_dir/output.9	/	ext4
654	0	15483593433758586291	POSIX_BYTES_WRITTEN	0	/home/belen/github/cern/test_dir/output.9	/	ext4
655	0	15483593433758586291	POSIX_MAX_BYTE_READ	13	/home/belen/github/cern/test_dir/output.9	/	ext4
656	0	15483593433758586291	POSIX_MAX_BYTE_WRITTEN	0	/home/belen/github/cern/test_dir/output.9	/	ext4
657	0	15483593433758586291	POSIX_CONSEC_READS	0	/home/belen/github/cern/test_dir/output.9	/	ext4

Figure 2: Example of the output of the darshan-parser utility. Each line corresponds to an I/O operation, summarised.

As one can see from the last Figure, we have 8 columns or features, where each entry contains information about an exact I/O call from a process. In particular, the I/O data may be sorted by the column *<counter>*, which indicates the operation type or what is being measured. For example, *POSIX_BYTES_READ* shows the totals number of bytes that exact/particular operation performed (we need to sum all operations to get the application total). There are several possible values for the counter column, but the most relevant ones (for our project) are the following:

- *POSIX_BYTES_READS*, *POSIX_BYTES_WRITES*: total number of bytes read or written, respectively.
- *POSIX_CONSEC_READS*, *POSIX_CONSEC_WRITES*: number of consecutive read or write operations, after the first one. If for reading a file, 8 read operations have been executed, then the value of this entry would be 7.
- *POSIX_MAX_BYTE_READ*, *POSIX_MAX_BYTE_WRITTEN*: number of bytes of the read or write operation than is the maximum between all of them.
- *POSIX_ACCESS1_ACCESS*: number of bytes (or size) of the operation that is the most frequent. For example, if from 10 write operations, 9 of them have a size of 1KB, then the value of this entry would be 9000 (in bytes).

Using the Python module of Darshan to parse the log files, called *PyDarshan*, we will extract this information, process it and transform them into the parameters that IOR handles. This translation is detailed in section 2.4.

2.2.1 Limitations

Up until the date this report was written, the latest up-to-date version of Darshan does not fully support containers. It gives unreliable information about the I/O operations performed by applications within a container. In addition, for Python scripts, there is a known issue with

the *multiprocessing* library, where some I/O calls are not counted, so every application that uses it will not be reliably profiled by Darshan [4].

2.3 IOR

Before detailing the methodology used to translate the output of Darshan to I/O requirement values, we have to introduce IOR. IOR is a well established benchmark that tests parallel filesystems. It is very flexible, as it works with a lot of options or flags to build and fit the tests to our current needs. The most relevant parameters to control the tests are:

- **SegmentCount**: a segment is a contiguous chunk of data accessed by multiple clients each writing/reading their own contiguous data (blocks).
- **blockSize**: size (in bytes) of a contiguous chunk of data accessed by a single client. It is comprised of one or more transfers.
- **transferSize**: size (in bytes) of a single data buffer to be transferred in a single I/O call.
- **numTasks**: number of tasks (or processes) that should participate in the test.

Which are best illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: SegmentCount, blockSize, transferSize and numTasks, are parameters that model access patterns in IOR. Taken from [5].

The flags **writeFile** and **readFile** indicate if the test should write and read test files respectively. A single application can have different behaviors for reading or writing, therefore, these tests are to be done separately, with each handling different values for the aforementioned parameters. The output of the tests shows write and read rates in Mebibytes per second (MiB/s). If the test is repeated several times, then the mean, standard deviation, min and max rates are also included. An example is shown in Figure 4.

Another aspect to consider when running IOR is the type of program we want to test. IOR has an **API** parameter that can take one of the values: POSIX, MPIIO, HDF5, ..., MMAP, or RADOS. The semantics of the parameters can vary depending on the API used by the application. For example, when using HDF5, the **segmentCount** parameter corresponds to the number of datasets handled by the application. We have to take into account this aspect when processing the output of Darshan.


```
Results:
access  bw(MiB/s)  IOPS    Latency(s)  block(KiB)  xfer(KiB)  open(s)  wr/rd(s)  close(s)  total(s)  iter
-----  -
write   7011        438.57  0.463954    65536       16384      0.008900  2.33      0.707985  2.34      0
read    6176        386.27  0.533662    65536       16384      0.180169  2.65      0.791301  2.65      0
remove  -           -       -           -           -          -         -         -         0.107673  0
write   7942        496.80  0.475753    65536       16384      0.027062  2.06      0.450800  2.06      1
read    5923        370.38  0.453971    65536       16384      0.099232  2.76      1.43      2.77      1
remove  -           -       -           -           -          -         -         -         0.102075  1
write   8014        501.37  0.442369    65536       16384      0.151156  2.04      0.321556  2.04      2
read    6044        377.98  0.504938    65536       16384      0.125744  2.71      1.17      2.71      2
remove  -           -       -           -           -          -         -         -         0.102300  2
write   6909        432.18  0.483409    65536       16384      0.009997  2.37      0.763071  2.37      3
read    5654        353.66  0.628601    65536       16384      0.215685  2.90      1.24      2.90      3
remove  -           -       -           -           -          -         -         -         0.114988  3
write   2820.63    176.35  0.453071    65536       16384      0.265339  5.81      4.11      5.81      4
read    6259        391.42  0.540062    65536       16384      0.179251  2.62      1.21      2.62      4
remove  -           -       -           -           -          -         -         -         0.115358  4
Max Write: 8014.41 MiB/sec (8403.72 MB/sec)
Max Read:  6258.60 MiB/sec (6562.61 MB/sec)

Summary of all tests:
Operation  Max(MiB)  Min(MiB)  Mean(MiB)  StdDev  Max(OPs)  Min(OPs)  Mean(OPs)  StdDev  Mean(s)  Stonewall(s)  S
b$
write      8014.41   2820.63   6539.55    1914.00   500.90    176.29    400.72    119.67   2.12400   NA
671088$
read       6258.60   5654.25   6011.10    212.01    391.16    353.39    375.69    13.25   2.72909   NA
671088$
Finished   : Fri Jul 29 05:59:32 2022
```

Figure 4: Example of the output of an IOR test, with 5 repetitions. The red box highlights the summary/statistics of the read and write rates.

2.4 Translating I/O requirements

We already saw what parameters we need to pass to IOR to run the benchmark. As stated in the beginning of this section, we will first focus on single-process programs, that use the common POSIX API. Therefore, the way of computing each of the parameters goes according to this type of program.

2.4.1 Number of tasks (numTasks)

Its value will be fixed to 1, because we are working with single process programs. This also implies that, for our tests, every segment will contain only one block, so the total number of blocks will be equal to the total number of segments (recall the structure seen in Figure 3).

2.4.2 Transfer size

The semantics of this parameter corresponds to the usual access size of each read or write call. From the Darshan log file we can get the values of the most frequent accesses by checking the POSIX_ACCESS1_ACCESS entries. The transfersize will be then the arithmetic mean of these values. Nevertheless, because in the IOR source code, the transfersize is constrained to be a multiple of the size of the *long long data type* (which is 8 bytes), we have to round the obtained mean to the closes integer that follows this constrain. For smaller file operations, mdTest (part of the IOR project) may be used.

```
transfersize = round(entries['POSIX_ACCESS1_ACCESS'].mean())
# transfersize and blocksize should be multiples of lon long type
# which is 8 bytes
transfersize = transfersize if transfersize % 8 == 0 else transfersize -
↳ (transfersize % 8)
```


Listing 1: Code snippet that shows how the `transfersize` parameter is calculated.

2.4.3 Block size

According to its definition, the data contained in a block is read by a single process, and is contiguous. Hence, we can make it equivalent to all the data contained in a file, which is read or written through several consecutive I/O calls. Finally, its computation is as follows:

```
# depending on the operation, we could also take the 'POSIX_CONSEC_READS'
  ↪ values
consec_ops = round(entries['POSIX_CONSEC_WRITES'].mean())
# if only one read or write call is made, then the value of
  ↪ POSIX_CONSEC_WRITES will be 0
consec_ops = consec_ops if consec_ops > 0 else 1
blocksize = transfersize * consec_ops
```

Listing 2: Code snippet that shows how the `blockSize` parameter is calculated.

2.4.4 Number of segments (`segmentCount`)

Its computations is a bit tricky, but it will be approximately equivalent to the number of files read or written. The segment count times the block size is the amount of data written or read by each process [1]. Because we only have one-process programs, this implies that the number of segments times the block size should equal all the bytes read or written by an application. So, we could compute the number of segments by dividing the total amount of bytes read or written by the block size. However, recall that because we computed the block size by using the arithmetic mean of the number of consecutive operations, then a block could be greater in size than the size of the files our program is dealing with in real life. Therefore, we have to quantify this excess of bytes and subtract it somehow. In addition, we would like to use the semantics of the number of segments to be approximate to the number of files (or datasets for data applications) in the computation of this parameter. Finally, this would be a code snippet of the computation of the `segmentCount`:

```
excess_io = (blocksize * total_files) - bytes_read
# for single process programs, one segment has one block, so both are
  ↪ equivalent
excess_blocks = floor(excess_io/blocksize)
segmentcount = total_files - excess_blocks
```

Listing 3: Code snippet that shows how the `segmentCount` parameter is calculated.

3 TESTS AND RESULTS

We benchmarked a Python script that can either write or read files. The sizes of the files varied from the 10MB to the 10 GB, each time increasing by one order of magnitude. Ten files were read or written per test, and 5 repetitions per test configuration were made. We ran the tests on a single node using a broadwell node type that uses a Ceph file system, with 1TB of storage and 512GB of RAM. The broadwell nodes are connected over 10Gb/s Ethernet to the central

storage resources at FI [2]. To get a measure of the real performance of the programs and make comparisons with our developed benchmark, we used a Python line profiler [3]. This was more convenient than using a timer, because there is also some added overhead when interpreting the Python scripts and opening/closing the files. With the line profiler, we could take the time of just the read or write operations, and so to calculate a more precise read or write rates.

3.1 Write tests

We first make a comparison of the computed load (the one estimated by our benchmark, based on the output of Darshan) against the real load. This is illustrated in Figure 5:

Figure 5: Comparison between the computed and real load, in mebibytes. Both axes are in log scale.

We can appreciate an almost linear curve, meaning that there is a minimal variation between the real and computed loads. This is an indicator that the calculation of the IOR parameters is well tuned. Next, we compare the write rates estimated by IOR against the real ones, obtained with the Python line profiler. See Figure 6:

Figure 6: Comparison between the write rates, real (left) and computed with our benchmark (right). The horizontal axes are in log scale and the vertical lines represent standard deviations.

We note that the performance reflected in both scenarios are different. In the curve on the left, there is a sudden drop when the total load is 1 GiB. There might have been some interruption in the node that delayed the I/O operations in that point, as this is the lowest

write rate in comparison to the ones achieved with greater loads. On the graph on the right, we see that the write rates increase when the bigger the loads are, however it seems to reach a plateau after the 10 GiB load. The difference in the curves could come from measuring the bandwidths without bypassing the cache, so IOR is mostly measuring the performance of our node's memory.

3.2 Read tests

Following the same order as before, we present the comparisons for loads and read rates, in Figures 7,8:

Figure 7: Comparison between the computed and real load, in mebibytes. Both axes are in log scale.

Figure 8: Comparison between the read rates, real (left) and computed with our benchmark (right). The horizontal axes are in log scale and the vertical lines represent standard deviations.

As we can see in Figure 7, the loads were precisely estimated, just as before. In Figure 8, we see a big difference in the values of the read rates, where IOR almost triples the real values. This is an indicator that cache is being hit. For read tests, bypassing the cache is more tricky. The read tests were performed with the *fsync* option, that performs fsync upon POSIX write close operations. The *fsync* call flushes the data from memory, and so it's useful when trying to avoid cache. Nevertheless this seems to be not enough to defeat page caching. Currently, IOR provides options that make use of parallel processing so that nodes deal with the batch of

data they haven't worked on before. But for our particular test scenario, we have to be more clever. The two possible workarounds are:

- Limit the memory space available to the node.
- Pass a hint to the kernel that evicts the cache.

In summary, we were able to precisely compute the required workloads of the applications. On the other hand, the measurement of bandwidth turned out to be a challenge, specially for single-process applications, where a node has to trick itself.

4 RECOMMENDATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Because the tendency in CERN is to include AI/ML in more of their projects, future work should follow that line. More tests are needed to tweak the computation of the parameters to pass to IOR, defeat the cache and make our pipeline generalizable. To overcome mislead measurements due to page caching, two solutions were proposed. In addition, tests of applications that use HDF5, a now popular dataset format, and that run on multiple nodes and use GPU, is needed. It is also important to note that IOR is intended to measure peak performance, and not what an application does in real life. There will be cases in which applications leverage the cache, e.g.: when it is needed to read the same chunks of data several times during its execution. The developed benchmark should consider this and offer the possibility to not bypass cache.

5 REFERENCES

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